

Multilingual and Low-Resource Named Entity Recognition

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Stripe org acquires **Nigeria loc**'s **Paystack org** for \$200M+ to expand into **the African continent loc** <https://tcrn.ch/3j2mnS3> by @ingridlunden

Stripe org rachète la startup **nigériane loc** **Paystack org** pour 200 millions de dollars afin de s'implanter sur **le continent Africain loc** <https://tcrn.ch/3j2mnS3> @ingridlunden

स्ट्राइप org ने \$200M+ में **नाइजीरिया loc** के **पेस्टेक org** को **अफ्रीकी महाद्वीप loc** में विस्तारित करने के लिए अधिग्रहित किया <https://tcrn.ch/3j2mnS3> @ingridlunden

Nigeria (Q1033)

sovereign state in West Africa
Federal Republic of Nigeria | NG | FRN | NGA | NGF

WIKIDATA

▼ In more languages

Language	Label
English	Nigeria
Hindi	नाईजीरिया
Achinese	Nigeria
Adyghe	Нигерие
Tunisian Arabic (Arabic script)	نيجيريا
Afrikaans	Nigeria

Results

Lang	Dataset	Lookup	Mono. Training	Mul. Training	Mono. Training + WikiANN	Mul. Training + WikiANN
en	CoNLL-2003	36.6	40.2	38.3	47.2	43.2
de	CoNLL-2003	22.8	35.5	36.6	41.2	39.6
nl	CoNLL-2002	36.8	39.4	43.2	55.4	52.8
es	CoNLL 2002	29.7	27.4	29.1	37.6	44.0
fr	xLIME	15.6	27.7	26.4	30.3	32.6
it	xLIME	23.3	29.3	28.9	28.4	25.4
tr	JRC	22.9	24.8	28.0	27.8	28.6
hi	SEAS	20.4	11.8	9.8	14.0	8.3
ar	CS-18	16.7	22.8	14.0	21.9	11.3

Mono. = Monolingual, Mul. = Multilingual
Metric: Entity-based Micro-Averaged F1 for the detection and tagging of Persons, Locations and Organizations